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THE IMPORTANCE AND ROLE OF MEDIA IMAGE IN THE STRATEGIC DEVELOPMENT AND CONTEMPORARY REPUTATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Nazarov Gulom

Press Secretary of the Information and Media Service of TSUE

Abstract: This article analyzes the formation of image as a key element in the strategic development of higher education institutions (HEIs). In today's educational landscape, HEIs face the challenge of creating and sustaining a competitive image in a global context. The study explores various approaches to understanding the image of HEIs, defining it as the distinctive characteristics that set an institution apart from its competitors. The HEI image is categorized into four main components: internal, regional, national, and international.

To enhance competitiveness and maintain a strong position in the global market, universities prioritize strengthening their image. In this process, media channels including the internet, social networks, academic journals, and university-produced lectures play a crucial role. Universities seek global recognition by promoting their values, scientific achievements, and student services through these platforms.

The article highlights the media image as a vital factor in strategic development and overall competitiveness. As local and international markets evolve, HEIs are increasingly focusing on updating and promoting their media presence. The study provides an analysis of modern marketing strategies for developing the image of HEIs during their transformation and strategic growth phases.

Key words: HEIs, reputation, image, media, marketing, transformation, digitalization.

INTRODUCTION

In today's highly competitive environment, organizations across all sectors seek to gain an edge that sets them apart. Among the key factors contributing to competitiveness are a well-developed corporate culture, a strong and positive image, and a recognized brand. The concept of image, as a crucial element of strategic positioning, first gained academic and practical attention abroad. Early significant research on image formation emerged in Western countries, particularly in the United States, where, by the mid-20th century, the term *image* was used to describe mechanisms for enhancing the perceived value of products. Over the following decades, businesses and scholars expanded the concept beyond consumer goods, recognizing its broader role in organizational success.

By the 1980s, companies in the United Kingdom had begun actively developing practical solutions aimed at strengthening corporate image as a means of gaining a competitive advantage. Around the same period, businesses in the United States increasingly turned to image formation technologies, integrating branding strategies into their corporate development models. These developments reflected a growing understanding that a strong image contributes not only to market positioning but also to stakeholder trust and long-term success.

In Uzbekistan, the concept of image entered professional discourse much later. Its theoretical foundations began to take shape with the emergence of research in the field of imageology, which analyzed the role of image formation in various sectors. The 1990s marked a period when the strategic importance of image became evident for higher education institutions, prompting both theoretical exploration and practical applications. Over the past few decades, scholars from Uzbekistan and abroad have increasingly focused on the mechanisms of

image formation and dissemination, examining its relationship with closely related concepts such as branding and reputation. These studies have considered the role of image not only in corporate settings but also in relation to products and services, organizations, geographical regions, and even individuals. As the global landscape continues to evolve, the importance of image as a strategic asset remains a central topic in academic and business discussions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scholars such as Prokhorov A.V., Efimova I.N., Alyoshina I.V., Golubkov E.P., Sharykov F.I., Ilinsky S.V., D.A. Aaker, T. Gad, F. Kotler, J.J. Lambin, and D. Ogilvy have conducted a series of studies on this topic. In particular, Ivanova Yu.O.'s scientific article, "*Image as a Factor in Promoting Universities in the Context of Export-Oriented Higher Education*," examines the issues of shaping and enhancing the image of universities from the perspective of exporting higher education systems in the context of globalization. The article highlights the importance of image and its formation processes in ensuring the competitiveness of higher education institutions on an international scale. It also provides specific recommendations on how universities can strengthen their reputation both globally and nationally.

The issue of competition has not bypassed higher education institutions. In addition to competing for the most outstanding applicants and highly qualified academic and pedagogical staff, universities also engage in competition at the level of institutional image and reputation. O.V. Frolova's scholarly article, "*Image as a Condition for University Competitiveness*," explores the role and significance of institutional image in ensuring university competitiveness in modern conditions. The article emphasizes the necessity for universities to enhance their international competitiveness in the context of globalization. The study addresses issues related to university brand positioning, image and brand management, brand promotion technologies, and rebranding, as discussed by scholars such as G. Drori, I.A. Anisimova (Kraeva), O.I. Belyaeva, V.V. Volkova, I.V. Gvozdeckaya, I.V. Groshev, E.A. Dagaeva, Yu.Yu. Zvezdochkina, E.A. Neretina, A.P. Pankrukhina, B.Yu. Serbinovsky, V.V. Sibirev, A.V. Skripkina, G.F. Sunyagin, N.R. Khachatryan, O.V. Frolova, G.R. Yusupova, and others.

Research on the challenges of building the international image of universities remains increasingly relevant, particularly in the context of higher education export. However, certain theoretical and practical aspects of university image and brand construction—especially the distinctive characteristics of international university image-building—require further development. Y.O. Ivanova justifiably underscores the necessity of a deeper exploration of the principles, methods, and factors that determine the international and export-oriented image of higher education institutions [1]. The strengthening of the international image of several foreign universities began in 2013.

Despite numerous studies on various types of images and the formation of imageology as a scientific and practical field, the ambiguity of the term "*image*" remains unresolved. The English word "*image*" (derived from the Latin "*imago*," meaning representation or likeness) has multiple meanings, such as "*reflection*," "*depiction*," and "*copy*," which complicates its interpretation [2]. According to I.V. Alyoshina, the concept of "*image*" is often understood in an overly simplistic and superficial manner, leading to the development of image-formation technologies that focus primarily on cosmetic solutions [3].

In his works, Philip Kotler defines *image* as "*the public perception of a company or its products*" [4]. Frequently, the term "*image*" is used interchangeably with "*representation*," "*reputation*," and "*public opinion*." This usage reflects how an organization's standing, as well as the perception of its products and services, is shaped by public attitudes, consumer perspectives, and client evaluations.

Psychologists emphasize that an image should be viewed as a structured and systematic entity rather than a completely random construct. Building an image requires working with stereotypes embedded in public consciousness. In A.Y. Panasyuk's works, an image is understood as a manipulative and engaging psychological representation, inherently designed for perception [5]. It is formed based on the communicative characteristics, expectations, and demands of collective consciousness. An image generates a strong emotional impact, simultaneously incorporating elements of both illusion and realism.

Furthermore, an image is pragmatic, meaning it is directed toward specific objectives that align with an organization's goals or the dynamics of a given situation. It is inherently active, influencing individuals' cognition and behavior. Since an image cannot be directly measured, it can only be evaluated through interactions, activities, and choices. Additionally, it possesses a stereotypical nature [6]. An image is constructed by selecting distinct characteristics that set it apart from the general mass [7]. The more carefully chosen these characteristics are, the stronger their impact will be. Therefore, only those traits that are strategically designed to ensure initial success should be selected.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research approach, relying on secondary data sources such as academic literature, university reports, media content, and global rankings. A thematic analysis was conducted to identify key patterns in HEI image formation, focusing on branding, media influence, and competitive positioning. The research examines successful institutional strategies for strengthening image at regional, national, and international levels. While the study provides valuable insights, its reliance on secondary data may limit access to internal institutional perspectives. Additionally, the rapidly evolving digital landscape should be considered when interpreting the findings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In communication theory, an image is defined as the representation of a real event, phenomenon, person, or institution, shaped by personal interaction experiences, mass media, rumors, advertisements, and the professional activities of image-makers [8]. The concept of "image" is often associated with related notions such as "reputation," "status," and "authority" [9].

Reputation refers to an evaluative set of information regarding an entity's qualities, advantages, and shortcomings. It is understood as a form of public assessment and one of the key characteristics of an image, shaped by perceptions of an object's strengths and weaknesses. In marketing, status denotes the special value of products or services, indicating their appeal to consumers with higher social standing and aligning with their "brand" identity [10].

Regarding higher education institutions (HEIs), reputation is frequently used synonymously with image: "a strong public opinion about an HEI, formed through direct interactions or information obtained from other sources." The reputation of an HEI has gained significant importance with the advancement of social networks, which have made it possible to assess its presence within the media environment [11]. The image itself pertains to the perceived value of a higher education institution's (HEI) media environment and is analyzed alongside its mission, corporate culture, and brand. A strong image contributes to solving both communication and economic challenges [12]. Examining image from an economic perspective allows for the differentiation between its qualitative and quantitative characteristics. Qualitative characteristics are determined by economic, environmental, and financial needs, whereas quantitative characteristics include its *goodwill* value [13]. For higher education institutions (HEIs), considering economic efficiency is essential in the context of attracting funding from various sources and engaging in commercial activities, both of which can be achieved through a positive image. According to Y.Y. Zvezdochkina and B.Y. Serbinovsky, a positive image enhances the value of the services provided, making it a factor that determines the volume of an organization's intangible assets [14].

The image of a higher education institution has acquired new significance within the framework of social media technologies due to academic activities, as HEIs are increasingly viewed as competitive enterprises oriented toward the commercialization of various fields of activity. V.V. Volkova and O.V. Frolova define academic image as a set of characteristics that distinguish an HEI, recorded in specific symbols and informational forms, which are deliberately created and transmitted through internal and external communications to various target audiences [15]. These characteristics are perceived and evaluated by the audience, subsequently becoming ingrained in their consciousness as stereotypes, thereby influencing their future actions toward the HEI [16].

Many researchers emphasize the evaluative component of an HEI's image. Y.Y. Zvezdochkina and B.Y. Serbinovsky define the image of an educational institution as a combination of positive impressions, status, and reputation, which are purposefully formed and maintained among various audiences through rational and emotional means of influence [17]. Image contributes to the creation of additional, non-depreciable value, facilitating institutional success, enhancing competitiveness, and strengthening the institution's position in the market for educational and scientific services.

N.R. Khachatryan also highlights the significance of the evaluative component in understanding image and suggests that it should be examined through students' assessments of the educational product [18]. From his perspective, students determine the evaluation of a higher education institution, as they assess not only the competence of the educational process but also the institution's potential in the labor market. A crucial aspect of the image formation process is its dependence on two interrelated components: the informational (descriptive) component, which represents a set of perceptions describing the institution and its image, and the evaluative component, which reflects the attitudes of target audiences toward the educational institution [19].

Figure 1. A crucial component in the formation of the image of a higher education institution (HEI) in relation to its potential in the labor market.

These components are interconnected and collectively form a comprehensive image. The evaluation of a higher education institution (HEI) is often based on its experience, third-party opinions, values, and national principles. The process of image formation is also influenced by external factors, such as state activities. V.V. Sibirev emphasizes the role of the state in shaping the image of higher education institutions (HEIs) and highlights the significant impact of state policy in the field of education on the perception of HEIs [20]. The regulation of educational activities by the state—including licensing, accreditation, and monitoring of HEI effectiveness affects their reputation and image.

An analysis of existing approaches to image formation within organizations allows for the identification of the following elements (“layers”) of image, which, depending on the target audience, constitute various types of images: internal image (II), regional image (RI), national image (NI), and international image (II).

The potential of higher education institutions (HEIs) in the labor market and the process of shaping their image are closely linked to two key components:

Figure 2. Image layers of a higher education institution based on the target audience.

The diagram illustrates the interconnection between these levels. In our view, the national image serves as the foundation for building an international image. However, the interaction may also occur in the reverse direction: an established international image can positively influence the institution’s national and regional images. Each image level depicted is reflected in the media outlets of higher education institutions. The internal image of a higher education institution encompasses the perceptions held by its faculty, researchers, and students, as well as the image of the educational services and specific academic programs it offers. Factors that shape the internal image include the institution’s corporate culture and the socio-psychological environment within the organization. Understanding the essence of modern organizations and their activities reveals a direct connection between the internal image of a higher education institution and its national culture.

Internal image (II) — The perception of the higher education institution by its faculty, researchers, and students, including the image of its educational services and academic programs.

Regional image (RI) — The perception of the higher education institution at the regional or city level.

National image (NI) — The perception of the higher education institution at the national level, based on its reputation, academic achievements, and contributions to societal development.

International image (II) — The global perception of the higher education institution, shaped by its position in the international arena, student exchange programs, and scientific collaborations.

Figure 3. Description of the image layers of the higher education institution according to the target audience.

Research indicates that event-based communications play a crucial role in creating a positive internal image. Elements of event-based communications include traditional events (such as ceremonies dedicated to students, meetings, competitions, and Olympiads) as well as public events that reflect the uniqueness of each higher education institution. For example, at Tashkent State University of Economics, the opening ceremony of the *Students' League* sports competition took place. The event was attended by prominent officials, including the Minister of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation, distinguished representatives of the Ministry of Higher Education, and university graduate Asila Mirzayev, a gold medalist and record holder at the Paris 2024 Paralympic Games, who proudly delivered a speech highlighting her connection to the university [21]. This event holds great significance for the institution's regional, internal, national, and international image, emphasizing the importance of showcasing such achievements.

As mentioned above, presenting the work carried out in internationally recognized fields of higher education institutions through media outlets is a key factor in shaping their international image. In particular, Uzbekistan's leading publications emphasize the alignment of educational programs with international demands and standards, the introduction of advanced foreign practices into the national education system, and the preparation of highly qualified personnel capable of meeting market demands. It was widely promoted that Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE) successfully passed international accreditation for five of its bachelor's programs [22]. News outlets have highlighted the university's systematic efforts to provide high-quality education that meets international standards, aiming to prepare competitive professionals for today's labor market. This serves as an essential tool for strengthening both the international and local image of the institution. International universities and organizations increasingly recognize and trust the university's position on the global stage, acknowledging the systematic efforts undertaken in this regard. Furthermore, this serves as a strong promotional tool for prospective students, reinforcing their confidence in choosing this institution for international education. Practical efforts aimed at enhancing the local and international image of national universities can be observed. Specifically, the widely promoted lecture held by Nobel Laureate Hiroshi Amano at the National University of Uzbekistan contributed significantly to the institution's academic reputation and visibility [23]. Over time, such events gain additional significance and actively contribute to strengthening the university's external standing, increasing its recognition among broader public circles. The university's corporate media channels, particularly those covering special events, serve as primary platforms for promoting these

initiatives. It is worth noting that the regional image of a higher education institution is assessed based on the following criteria: the quality of education, the diversity of services offered, the employment rate of graduates, the cost of services, and the university's contributions to regional socio-economic development.

Figure 4. Criteria for enhancing the regional image of higher education institutions.

There is evaluative (assessing) information regarding these parameters, which is carried and disseminated by individuals who have experience studying at the higher education institution, such as relatives, friends, and acquaintances. For regional higher education institutions, this component of the image holds greater priority for several reasons. First, regional institutions traditionally focus on *internal acceptance*, with prospective students—and later, enrolled students—coming primarily from the region where the institution operates. Typically, universities have a well-defined reputation within their respective regions. For example, the National University of Uzbekistan is one of the leading institutions in the region in terms of student enrollment, particularly among foreign students, and offers a wider range of educational programs compared to other regional institutions. Second, higher education institutions in the regions continue to maintain their status as scientific, innovative, educational, and cultural centers. These universities provide the region with a skilled workforce that contributes to socio-economic development. In this regard, universities often emphasize their brand attributes, such as slogans (for example, the slogan of TDIU: «A higher institution preparing the builders of the future»).

It should be emphasized that in recent years, the process of globalization in the Republic of Uzbekistan has directly influenced the socio-political and financial interconnections within the higher education system. The Decree of the President No. DP-2909¹ [24] of April 20, 2017, “On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System”, the Decree of the President No. DP-5847² [25] of October 8, 2019, “On the Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” outline key tasks aimed at expanding opportunities for reforming the higher education system, accelerating development trends, integrating education and production, and enhancing financial stability. As a result, over the past seven years, the number of higher education institutions has increased from 77 to 212. The enrollment rate of school graduates in higher education has quadrupled in the same period [27]. By 2024, 310,000 young people are expected to be admitted to the country's higher education institutions. Additionally, 40 state higher education institutions have been granted academic and financial independence, enabling them to ensure financial stability, strengthen their material and technical base, and independently determine admission quotas for contract-based students [28]. A new procedure has also been introduced, allowing each higher education institution to independently develop and approve curricula and educational programs [29].

This has fostered a competitive environment in the education system and stimulated further competition among higher education institutions to improve quality. As mentioned, the increase in the number of state and non-state higher education institutions has contributed to shaping a competitive environment in higher education, enhancing the quality of education, and strengthening the country's international standing. In this process, media image—the positive representation of higher education institutions in mass media—plays a crucial role in attracting students and enhancing institutional competitiveness.

With the formation of a competitive environment, each university strives to differentiate itself by offering unique study conditions, research opportunities, and student-oriented facilities. This competition has also heightened the significance of media image in attracting students, as institutions focus on showcasing their strengths through various media channels. The growing competition among higher education institutions has made the positive cultivation of their media image a vital task. Establishing a strong presence in mass media and social networks is one of the most effective strategies for attracting young people. Institutions highlight

1 <https://lex.uz/docs/3171587>

2 <https://www.lex.uz/en/docs/6971334>

their achievements, international collaborations, modern infrastructure, and high-quality education processes to appeal to prospective students.

In student recruitment, higher education institutions promote their offerings through a positive image. When choosing a university, young people consider not only academic programs but also the institution's reputation, campus environment, and additional opportunities. By strengthening their image, universities emphasize their uniqueness—an essential factor in a competitive environment. Both state and non-state higher education institutions are creating extensive opportunities to enhance their competitiveness. Promoting these diverse opportunities through media channels helps institutions reach wider audiences. Moreover, universities leverage social networks to create positive impressions by showcasing the best aspects of student life. Universities also offer students global experiences through international exchange programs and faculty collaboration with foreign academics. Additional opportunities include various scholarships, joint educational programs with international universities, internship placements, and practical experience in innovative laboratories. These initiatives play a crucial role in shaping a university's positive image, increasing its international recognition, and attracting students.

According to statistical research, a strong media image significantly influences students and their parents when selecting an educational institution. On a global scale, universities gain international recognition through their media presence. For example, achieving high rankings in international assessments such as QS and Times Higher Education strengthens an institution's media image and builds trust. Therefore, the increasing number of state and non-state higher education institutions, along with the diversity of offerings and opportunities, has made media image and social engagement key factors. Through a positive media image, higher education institutions can attract not only domestic but also international students, further enhancing their global competitiveness. At the same time, ensuring the sustainable development of the education system and securing high positions in international rankings requires continuous focus on media image and institutional competitiveness.

It should be noted that the national image of a higher education institution (HEI) is directly related to its role in training specialists for the country's economy. In this context, research and state HEIs occupy leading positions. The place of an HEI in national rankings is also a crucial factor in shaping its national image, as these rankings reflect the institution's achievements in scientific research and general education. For example, every year, the State Inspection for the Quality of Education in Uzbekistan publishes the national ranking of HEIs. In determining these rankings, the HEIs' specific areas of focus and key performance indicators are taken into account. Thus, the formation of an HEI's image should be based on information regarding its leading position in training specialists in specific fields, scientific research areas, staff potential, technical resources, and opportunities to work in the modern information environment. This process should aim to foster a positive public perception.

The growing significance of an HEI's international image is linked to the internationalization of higher education, which is considered one of the key outcomes of globalization. Internationalization implies strengthening the international dimension of HEI activities, including: academic mobility programs; joint educational programs; an increase in the number of foreign students, etc. [30]

From our perspective, the international image of an HEI refers to its current or desired perception in the global arena and its position in the global educational services market. The international image is often associated with the institution's placement in international rankings.

The international dimension of an HEI's activities is reflected in its:

- Scientific and educational internationalization
- Academic mobility of students and staff
- Standing in international rankings

Certainly, HEIs need to highlight their international status on their official websites, social media pages, and publications. Another key aspect of internationalizing HEI activities and shaping their international image is "education export." One of the most distinctive indicators of an HEI's international dimension is the academic mobility of students and faculty members. Official publications of HEIs frequently feature materials dedicated to academic mobility opportunities for academic staff, teachers, and students.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The positive image of a higher education institution (HEI) remains an additional competitive advantage in various markets. Competition among HEIs spans several areas, including attracting students (both in terms of quality and quantity), recruiting highly qualified staff (teachers and researchers), and securing funding from various sources. The competition regarding image and brand holds a distinct position as an independent competitive factor, directly influencing an institution's reputation.

As highlighted, multiple approaches exist for defining the structure of an HEI's image. Depending on the target audience, an HEI's image can be categorized as internal, regional, national, or international (global). These types of images are interconnected and do not function in isolation. Each type of image is reflected in an HEI's social media materials.

As analyzed in this article, several challenges hinder the effective image-building of HEIs in our country, including the lack of a comprehensive marketing strategy, the need for professional marketing teams, limited technological solutions, the implementation of modern technologies for social media platforms, insufficient financial resources, and the allocation of special funds from the HEI budget for media activities. To stay aligned with global changes, institutional policies and practices, marketing strategies, and higher education infrastructure must be continuously adapted.

In the context of global market competition, HEIs must focus on developing curricula that align with the real needs of their regions. They are increasingly engaging in benchmarking and network creation to strengthen their brand positioning and enhance their presence on social media platforms.

This article also recommends that institutional branding and competitive success require HEIs to be adaptable to changes in their marketing environment. Given the limitations of the traditional marketing mix (price, advertising, people, product, and planning), HEIs should adopt innovative and collaborative approaches to refine their marketing strategies. Implementing modern marketing strategies will enable institutions to identify key areas for improvement and develop effective solutions.

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